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The sources of Baltic oak

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ABSTRACT

Past trade in oak from the lands to the east and south of the Baltic Sea was extraordinary in that it dominated the Northern European market for specialized oak products for many centuries. Equally extraordinary is the fact that since the 1980s, when a large corpus of dendrochronological data from artworks was demonstrated to represent the material evidence for this past trade, we, until now, have not been able to pinpoint where, in this large region, the trees for this trade grew. Through our analysis we can now present the likely sources of three major timber groups in this material, and significantly, the new chronologies that we make available here, will be the key foundation for dating and identifying provenance of Baltic oak, for tree-ring research long into the future.

1. Introduction

A breakthrough in dendrochronology in the 1980s identified, for the first time, the material remains of the extensive trade of timber, particularly oak, from the Southern Baltic region into Western Europe. Oak panels, used as supports for artworks and ecclesiastical sculpture, dating from the mid-14th to the mid-17th centuries, were found to contain wood that matched to oak tree-ring chronologies derived from the region around the mouth of the Vistula River (Baillie et al., 1985; Eckstein et al., 1986). Our knowledge of the extent of this trade of oak timber over several centuries has increased substantially since, particularly as many more oak objects, artworks, ships and boats have been analysed dendrochronologically. Many of the objects analysed can, in terms of the similarity of the tree-ring patterns, be placed into discrete groups. These were called 'Baltic 1' and 'Baltic 2' with a less well replicated 'Baltic 3' (Hillam and Tyers 1995). These groups have a tendency to a chronological separation also, where Baltic 1 belongs to the earlier objects while Baltic 3 tend to be later works. These groups most likely represent oaks from geographically separate areas in the large territories south and east of the Baltic Sea coast, but since the breakthrough in the 1980s, we have been unable to pinpoint where these groups came from.

2. A short research history

Through the 1960s and 70s several different groups of pioneering dendrochronologists in Europe were working towards the creation of

continuous local oak tree-ring sequences (e.g. Fletcher 1978a, which includes chapters discussing regional data from Germany, Sweden, Poland, Netherlands and England amongst others). In the early years of dendrochronology in Northern Europe chronologies for oak were built from timbers from a range of historical buildings, subfossil trees in bogs and wetlands and from living trees, allowing a large network of oak chronologies from across Germany, Netherlands, Britain and Ireland to be absolutely dated. Each of these chronologies was constructed from timbers that were either entirely or mostly sourced locally, and this local origin was clear because they were linked to living tree chronologies derived from stands of oaks from across the entire area. Chronologies from artworks however presented a quite different problem because, while strong cross-matching between the tree-ring curves from many oak panels allowed robust chronologies representing this material to be built, the absolute dating of these remained disputed. It was at the time stated that "continuous importation of wood of the same provenance for over 200 years is hard to imagine" (Eckstein et al., 1975). Nine years later, Baillie published a detailed discussion on art-historical dendrochronology, pointing out many published examples of historical reference to the import of boards and planks from Prussia (Baillie 1984). Shortly after, two papers demonstrated dendrochronologically the eastern origin of the art-historical material (Baillie et al., 1985; Eckstein et al., 1986). It emerged, after the construction of a chronology for Northern Poland (Eckstein et al., 1986) that the painted oak panels were in fact dateable using this Polish chronology, and equally that the oak trees had grown somewhere in the south-eastern Baltic countries (Ważny 1990; Ważny and Eckstein 1987). This material was related to

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Fig. 1. Historical map of Old Prussia Gerardus Mercator, *Atlas sive cosmographica*, Duisburg 1595. <http://copernicus.torun.pl/en/biography/1473-1491/1/?view=gallery&file=1> accessed February 17, 2021 (two column).

an extensively documented trade in oak boards derived from the countries at the south-eastern end of the Baltic, including Poland.

The use of the ‘Baltic’ description however glosses over some significant variations that are evident within the material. It is possible to have a panel with three boards in it, which do not match each other, even though each is Baltic. The pioneers were aware of this, even before they realised it was non-local timber. John Fletcher published what he thought were English data sets in 1977 (Fletcher 1977) under the names REF1, 2 3 and 4 which subsequently were identified as Baltic and redated. Josef Bauch and others had found a similar situation in the Netherlands (Bauch, 1978; Eckstein et al., 1975) creating a Chronology I from local building timbers, and a parallel Chronology II from panel paintings. By 1978 it was known that REF1 and Chronology II exhibited remarkable similarities and they were assumed to be from a similar source, though at the time this was thought to be from somewhere in Western Europe (Bauch 1978 op. cit.; Fletcher 1978b). Fletcher subsequently combined his REFS2 & 3 into one series, and REFS1 & 4 into another, with NewREF14 identified as being very similar to Chronology II, and NewREF23 being slightly different. Subsequent work has continued to replicate these data sets from objects, buildings and excavations across western Europe.

This material has been referred to by dendrochronologists ever since under the shorthand or catchall term of Baltic or Eastern Baltic oak. It is ubiquitous in certain kinds of cultural artefact from the 14th century through to the mid-17th century. Boats, barrels, chests and other furniture, painted screens and other church fittings, coffins, wall panelling, wagons, floorboards have all been identified using this material (e.g. most recently Daly 2021; Daly et al., 2021a; Daly and Streeton 2017; Domínguez-Delmás et al., 2021; Klein 2010; Tyers 1996,

2015a, 2015b, 2010a, 2010b). However, the pre-eminent source of dendrochronological data of this type is in panel paintings. Early Netherlandish works, Tudor English portraits and Dutch Golden Age art by Rubens and Rembrandt and numerous other artists all typically utilised this material for 90% of the panels that have been analysed.

In 1995, Hillam and Tyers (1995) reworked Fletcher’s partial archive of data to create two series that are now widely used by workers in this field. These were named as BALTIC1 and BALTIC2 and are broadly similar to Fletcher’s REF and NewREF datasets since they use a subset of the same primary data. The key point was that they worked through this data in two different ways, independently of each other, one in the datasets numerical order and the other in its reverse order, one using more reference to signature sequences visible in the graphs and the other more reliant on computer correlations. Both approaches yielded a common pair of composite datasets, those we now know as BALTIC1 and BALTIC2. This resulted in two key conclusions; it discounted the possibility that the groupings that Fletcher had seen were the result of a founder bias in his data, and it also showed that the data could be grouped the same either mathematically or by traditional dendrochronological techniques. The Fletcher data is relatively low resolution, 0.1 mm at best, the published composite chronologies combined 64 series into BALTIC1 and 40 into BALTIC2, and Hillam & Tyers noted the presence of a single third type that was not included in either but was evidently also of Baltic origin, part of a group subsequently known as Baltic 3 (the Fletcher archive Baltic1:2:3 ratio was therefore c. 61%:38%:1%)

We know that such timber was transported not only from Gdansk (e.g. Bonde et al., 1997) but also from other Eastern Baltic towns such as Riga in Latvia (Zunde 1999). Work on building chronologies for the

Table 1
Cross-correlations between the three Baltic groups.

	2021BLT1	2021BLT2	2021BLT3
2021BLT1	*	12.15	12.1
2021BLT2	12.15	*	10.72
2021BLT3	12.1	10.72	*

Eastern Baltic States has been carried out by researchers there, but their historic material available is dominated by pine. It seems plausible that with the extensive export of oak to the west, that this material was seldom used in local structures. More than 30 years since the dendro-chronological evidence for trade in oak from the Baltic region was first found, we still do not fully understand where these groups of timber were coming from. The development of localised tree-ring chronologies from the region they are thought to come from has so far failed to link living tree data series to the art-historical material, so that there remains a gap between locally sourced data and the historical material.

3. Recent developments in the field

Since the 1990s, the Sheffield group had created a working dataset called Baltic 3, and a number of pre-1450's Baltic datasets. Baltic 3 included the otherwise distinctive single sequence of Fletchers, and a number of clearly related panel and furniture sequences. They also identified a subset in Baltic 1 from a group of ceiling panels in a building called Bowhill (Groves 2002), which was rapidly replicated by other panelling from a Winchester building (Lewis 1995; Miles and Haddon-Reece 1996). These four groupings were made available to Pascale Fraiture for her PhD thesis datasets (Fraiture 2009). Her work made the innovative use of shaded clustergrams to illustrate the groupings of the individual boards, and measured a large group of boards at a higher resolution than was possible during the pioneering work. The result was to replicate the Sheffield sequences but from entirely different objects. Her data was at 0.01 mm resolution, and identified 118 Baltic 1 type, nine of which were in the Bowhill subgroup, 26 Baltic 2 type, and nine Baltic 3 type (Fraiture's Baltic1:2:3 ratio was therefore c. 77%:17%:6%). It was immediately clear that her dataset and the Fletcher dataset had different ratios of these Baltic sub-types. The question that arose was whether these patterns were reflecting the period differences of these types of art, in England Baltic 2 seemed to predominate in the second half of the 16th century, whilst Baltic 3 predominates in the first half of the 17th century in the Netherlands, alternatively were these patterns reflecting different trading patterns into England compared to those into the Netherlands?

This paper therefore builds upon this earlier work by examining the

Table 2
Cross-correlations between the equally-replicated sub-groups of the three main Baltic groups. The Baltic 1 groups are highlighted with blue, the Baltic 2 groups in yellow and the Baltic 3 in green.

	2021BLT1B	2021BLT1a	2021BLT1b	2021BLT1c	2021BLT1d	2021BLT1e	2021BLT1f	2021BLT1x	2021BLT2a	2021BLT2b	2021BLT2c	2021BLT2d	2021BLT2e	2021BLT3a	2021BLT3b	2021BLT3c
2021BLT1B	*	20.92	13.62	18.39	17.93	19.25	19.97	5.92	6.68	8.16	3.75	6.54	6.5	6.6	5.84	6.58
2021BLT1a	20.92	*	18.06	23.71	15.97	20.83	19.7	14.02	6.61	8.75	6.76	10.74	9.69	8.92	9.49	9.24
2021BLT1b	13.62	18.06	*	18.05	18.63	18.22	17.71	13.22	7.31	7.26	4.63	9.22	7.48	8.97	10.11	8.64
2021BLT1c	18.39	23.71	18.05	*	19.24	23.77	23.46	14.44	6.83	8.17	5.22	7.67	7.03	9.27	7.97	9.05
2021BLT1d	17.93	15.97	18.63	19.24	*	16.91	18.27	14.18	8.49	8.34	8.59	9.39	9.25	8.94	8.96	8.39
2021BLT1e	19.25	20.83	18.22	23.77	16.91	*	17.53	13.54	7.92	8.97	5.88	9.47	7.23	10.89	10.13	10.07
2021BLT1f	19.97	19.7	17.71	23.46	18.27	17.53	*	15.20	9.45	9.22	8.94	9.56	9.32	11.03	10.07	10.06
2021BLT1x	5.92	14.02	13.22	14.44	14.18	13.54	15.20	*	5.87	7.57	7.65	8.35	9.79	7.39	8.46	8.26
2021BLT2a	6.68	6.61	7.31	6.83	8.49	7.92	9.45	5.87	*	23.37	14.54	18.11	16.79	6.70	7.14	7.13
2021BLT2b	8.16	8.75	7.26	8.17	8.34	8.97	9.22	7.57	23.37	*	22.38	14.3	20.4	7.73	9.64	8.46
2021BLT2c	3.75	6.76	4.63	5.22	8.59	5.88	8.94	7.65	14.54	22.38	*	14.92	14.58	6.45	8.46	7.9
2021BLT2d	6.54	10.74	9.22	7.67	9.39	9.47	9.56	8.35	18.11	14.3	14.92	*	18.05	8.52	9.41	8.19
2021BLT2e	6.5	9.69	7.48	7.03	9.25	7.23	9.32	9.79	16.79	20.4	14.58	18.05	*	7.51	8.87	8.33
2021BLT3a	6.6	8.92	8.97	9.27	8.94	10.89	11.03	7.39	6.70	7.73	6.45	8.52	7.51	*	27.46	25.98
2021BLT3b	5.84	9.49	10.11	7.97	8.96	10.13	10.07	8.46	7.14	9.64	8.46	9.41	8.87	27.46	*	26.56
2021BLT3c	6.58	9.24	8.64	9.05	8.39	10.07	10.06	8.26	7.13	8.46	7.9	8.19	8.33	25.98	26.56	*

Table 3
Cross-correlation between chronologies for Vilnius and Klaipeda.

		Start	end	Memel K	Kloak	viloak
Memel K	Memel Klaipėda, Lithuania (n = 8) (Brazauskas 2006)	AD1288	AD1580	*	14.2	5.93
Kloak	Klaipeda, Lithuania, oak (n = 62) (Vitas 2020)	AD1247	AD1552	14.2	*	8.36
viloak	Vilnius Castle, Lithuania, oak (n = 20) (Pukienė and Ozalas 2007)	AD1202	AD1530	5.93	8.36	*

apparent threefold nature of most Baltic data sets derived from objects of the period 1450–1650. We illustrate those divisions empirically and propose an extension to our current knowledge by dividing the Bowhill group and another new grouping out of Baltic 1. There are no currently identifiable similar sub-groups within Baltic 2 or Baltic 3. Secondly the increasing production of ‘native’ datasets for oak from across the eastern Baltic countries and further east and north (Pukienė and Ozalas 2007; Brazauskas 2006; Vitas 2020; Khasanov et al., 2021) has, at last, begun to allow us to circumscribe the areas of origin of this material. Here we explore one potential methodology by which we can utilise these local datasets and we propose some hypothetical origins for the Baltic data, based on the currently available datasets from these regions. The inter-relationship of the data clearly suggests they are from three adjacent regions, from this study we begin to understand broadly where these were. How to map those onto the ground in more detail in the absence of a comprehensive tree-ring network of well replicated local datasets is a longer-term task. In contrast to the extensive documentary evidence, from customs and other sources, at the western end of this long-lived trade, there is a shortage of documentary and other evidence about how the trade was organised, who ran it, and where it took place within our proposed source regions.

The three groups seem to represent different geographical sources of oak in the wider South and East Baltic territories. These trees which would have been felled, probably split into quarters, or even smaller sizes at source, were brought down to the coasts to finally arrive at the main exporting ports in the south and east Baltic coast (Gdansk and other sites in the Gulf of Gdansk, Königsberg, Riga) to be shipped west. As the historic map of Prussia reproduced in Fig. 1 suggests, these river routes present an important topographical feature to be recorded. There is a tendency that objects of the 14th and 15th centuries often are identified as belonging to Baltic 1, while later (16th and 17th century) material identifies as Baltic 3. There is also a tendency that the practice of splitting the tree trunks into planks is gradually replaced by mechanical sawing systems from the early part of the 17th century. This is reflected not only in the use of varying degrees of tangentially converted planks instead of radial, but also in observation of saw marks on the wood (Fraiture 2009; Wadum 1998).

Considering the historical dominance of the trade of timber from Gdansk, the Vistula River that flows from the southern border of modern-day Poland northwards to the gulf of Gdansk has long been the focus, for identifying this Baltic timber source (e.g. Haneca et al., 2005). River systems, of course, provided the lines of communication between regions, not least when dealing with heavy bulk commodities like timber. Extensive chronology building carried out by Ważny over many years has not thus far identified sources for the three Baltic groups in present-day Poland. Ważny has previously suggested that we should look further east (Ważny 2002) and he has later also presented a map outlining the theoretical progression, over time, of the source of Baltic oak, suggesting sources around the gulf of Gdansk for the 14th century, expanding southwards and eastwards in the 1st half of the 15th century and expanding further east again in the 2nd half of the 15th and the 16th centuries (Ważny 2005, 116).

Researchers in Lithuania have encountered oak material in several archaeological sites (Pukienė and Ozalas 2007; Brazauskas 2006). Pukienė has built chronologies for oaks found in Vilnius and in Klaipeda, in Lithuania. An additional Klaipeda chronology was also recently built (Vitas 2020). The Vilnius chronology spans the period AD 1202–1530 (n = 20) and the Klaipeda chronology spans AD 1266–1536 (n = 62). In the context of the collaboration in the TIMBER project, oak tree-ring data from a range of analyses were shared within the group. This meant that for the first time, we could compare the three main so-called Baltic groups with oak datasets from the east Baltic states.

4. Reassessment of the art-historical dataset

In Ważny (2002) comparisons between the two panel chronologies built by Hillam and Tyers (1995) and a network of Polish chronologies indicated that BALTIC2 demonstrated high correlation with a very broad series of datasets along the Vistula River while BALTIC1 agreed best with chronologies from sites around the gulf of Gdansk (Ważny 2002), although unfortunately his maps were swapped in the publication. His Fig. 3 (Ważny 2002, 317) represents the distribution for BALTIC2, while his Fig. 4 represents BALTIC1 (Ważny 2002, 318).

This paper seeks not only to present the status of the identification of

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the conjectural geographic relationship between the three art-historical dendrochronology groups, and between these three and the major adjacent geographical regions. This is a distance-free diagram but orientated like a map. The diagram illustrates how the authors interpret the relationship between the three Baltic groups as triangular, not linear. (single column).

Fig. 3. Map of the correlation between the Southern Baltic group ‘Baltic 1’ (2021BLT1) and master and site chronologies for oak for Northern Europe. The correlation statistic used is Student’s *t*-test (Student 1908) where the tree-ring data is normalised according to Baillie and Pilcher (1973). The circle on the map is sized according to the *t*-value. The underlying tree-ring dataset is described in Daly (2007a) but recent additions to this dataset for Lithuania, Latvia and Russia are added. The background map is from Natural Earth. Free vector and raster map data @ [naturalearthdata.com](http://www.naturalearthdata.com). Natural Earth (public domain): <http://www.naturalearthdata.com>. The river data is from Lehner and Grill (2013) (www.hydrosheds.org, accessed March 3, 2020). The map is generated using QGIS.org, 2021. QGIS Geographic Information System. QGIS Association. <http://www.qgis.org> (two column).

the source of the three ‘Baltic’ groups in the art-historical dataset. We have also re-worked the panel painting dataset, to confirm the groupings, and to attempt to suggest the region of origin of these groups using correlation statistics as a proxy for the distance in origin between sequences.

One of the issues with panel painting data is the problem of generating independent datasets. Except in the rare circumstance where a building has been sampled twice, or a linear feature extends between two excavations, it is rare to get the same tree featuring in two different tree-ring site chronologies based on living trees, buildings or archaeology. By contrast, panel painting data has three different forms of duplication. The majority of multi-board panels have duplicate parts of the same tree within different boards. Secondly, a single tree can have been used in more than one panel, and third, it is not unusual to re-analyse a panel that has been analysed by a previous generation of dendrochronologists. Indeed, it may be anticipated that future generations will continue to re-analyse either the same panels, or further panels that contain the same trees. To produce independent datasets, it is necessary to purge all this duplication, and whilst that is manageable for individual workers, it is almost impossible to manage that between workers. This analysis is intended to examine wider patterns of similarity and difference within independent sets of Baltic data, and for this purpose a series of similarly weighted groupings have been created, where no same trees (identified when tree-ring curves from separate boards achieve very high correlations and through confirmation by visual examination of the tree-ring curves), are spread across different sub-sets. These series are not independent of individual and composite datasets from other workers, but they are independent of each other.

A total of 1280 oak panel paintings and another 120 oak panel objects, analysed by one of us, comprising screens, doors, furniture & sculptures includes about 3000 analysed boards, with c. 2100 of those dated and identified as ‘Baltic’ in a broad sense. (The other dated oak boards are primarily English or Low Countries in origin). The western material is clearly separable from the eastern group by their cross-correlation with local Western European tree-ring chronologies and are not further considered here. This dataset does not include several other walling and door panel groups which were analysed as part of various buildings projects and it also excludes many archaeological groups of Baltic source timbers identified from boats, barrels, etc. At this stage, the earlier Baltic sources for the period c. AD 1300–1450 appear to be subtly different, and these will require similar analysis incorporating the more extensive archaeological datasets. The following analysis therefore applies to art-historical items made during the period c. AD 1450–1655.

The following analysis is driven by the data, not the art-historical context or background. All these items are made of riven or sawn oak boards of single radii, typically of near radial section. The data comprises relatively complete recording of the rings on at least one end of most of these boards, combined with outer edges of opposite ends where appropriate and possible. Some innermost rings were excluded either where edges were incomplete, or the material was more tangential and hence more difficult to record accurately. The data was recorded by one of us, over a period of almost 30 years, using the same methodology for almost the entire dataset (e.g. Tyers 2015a). It was almost exclusively gained by direct measurement to 0.01 mm precision of cleaned end grain, to a consistent standard, and at a consistent higher resolution than

Fig. 4. Map of the correlation between the Southern Baltic group 'Baltic 2' (2021BLT2) and master and site chronologies for oak for Northern Europe. The correlation statistic used is Student's *t*-test (Student 1908) where the tree-ring data is normalised according to Baillie and Pilcher (1973). The circle on the map is sized according to the *t*-value. The underlying tree-ring dataset is described in Daly (2007a) but recent additions to this dataset for Lithuania, Latvia and Russia are added. The background map is from Natural Earth. Free vector and raster map data @ [naturalearthdata.com](http://www.naturalearthdata.com). Natural Earth (public domain): <http://www.naturalearthdata.com>. The river data is from Lehner and Grill (2013) (www.hydrosheds.org, accessed March 3, 2020). The map is generated using QGIS.org, 2021. QGIS Geographic Information System. QGIS Association. <http://www.qgis.org> (two column).

the early datasets. None of this material was measured by hand-lens, most instead by use of electronics attached to travelling microscope stages, and some from digital photography. A handful of these projects use FIMO as proxy ends or used CT X-ray sections. Note that sapwood is rare throughout this material compared to other tree-ring data sets.

The identification of a same tree pair or triplet etc., within single multi-board items is commonplace, and identification of the same tree between different related and sometimes unrelated objects is frequent enough that these have been identified and combined for this project. Some individual trees are represented five or more times in different items within the dataset. Combining them in this way ensures there is no bias from them being over-weighted in the final composite chronologies. The 'same trees' within an item were typically identified during individual analyses and composite series representing a single tree were typically produced at that stage. Some trees between objects can typically only be identified some time after the analysis of the items involved. All these data have been compared with all other data and all high correlations reviewed, to determine whether the 'same trees' meet the criteria explained above. During analysis of individual panels, some same tree linkages can be identified by anatomical anomalies and other physical details, like identical knots or curvature, and some of these sequences were identified as individual trees on this basis, despite them having lower inter-correlations. Each of the 'same tree' groupings were combined into single 'tree' series. This reduced the data to 1411 series, where each can be given equal weighting when combined with others.

These 1411 Baltic series comprise 1048 individual boards where no same tree groupings were identified, 296 same tree groups of multiple boards from single panels or other items, and 67 same tree groups of

multiple boards from two or more items where this scenario was identified. The dataset is not independent of Fraiture, Fletcher or Klein. Fraiture's and this data contain a number of same tree matches, and one remeasurement of the same panel, similarly a significant number of panels previously analysed by Fletcher and Klein have been re-analysed, though here these are at much improved resolution. The material is a mixture 48% English panels, 46% Flemish, Netherlandish or Dutch panels, with the remaining 6% German, Spanish or French panels using Baltic oak, and a range of other types of British art-historical items including chests and church screens. These items broadly comprise 45% in British Institutional ownership, and 43% in either British private ownership or were analysed in British auction houses, galleries, conservation and restoration studios, where many of the latter categories will have been in private ownership at the time of analysis, 10% were in American Institutions, the remaining 2% were in American or European private ownership. Some are relatively low-status objects, others are exceptionally high status items. For reasons of discretion, privacy and ownership copyright it is inappropriate to identify this material in more detail. The Baltic material is currently classified as 682 Baltic 1 (including 2 sub-groups of Baltic 1 comprising 82 and 48 respectively), 449 Baltic 2, and 280 Baltic 3. These have been grouped here into a series of sub-composites, mostly with between 90 & 95 series in them. These have the advantage of illustrating the threefold nature of the data by demonstrating the same outcome is repeatable using any large enough and random enough group of panels and other objects. The Baltic 1, 2, 3 ratio is different from both Fletcher's and Fraiture's (c. 48%:32%:20%), we may hypothesise that this difference is because this is a larger number of panels from a wider range of places and periods.

Fig. 5. Map of the correlation between the Southern Baltic group ‘Baltic 3’ (2021BLT3) and master and site chronologies for oak for Northern Europe. The correlation statistic used is Student’s *t*-test (Student 1908) where the tree-ring data is normalised according to Baillie and Pilcher (1973). The circle on the map is sized according to the *t*-value. The underlying tree-ring dataset is described in Daly (2007a) but recent additions to this dataset for Lithuania, Latvia and Russia are added. The background map is from Natural Earth. Free vector and raster map data @ [naturalearthdata.com](http://www.naturalearthdata.com). Natural Earth (public domain): <http://www.naturalearthdata.com>. The river data is from Lehner and Grill (2013) (www.hydrosheds.org, accessed March 3, 2020). The map is generated using QGIS.org, 2021. QGIS Geographic Information System. QGIS Association. <http://www.qgis.org> (two column).

These items were not made in the east, they were made at the end of the supply chain since they frequently incorporate material from different Baltic sub-sources, and some incorporate both Baltic and local timbers.

The dataset was initially swept of multiple series derived from the same tree, since almost all multi-board panels use pairs or more of single trees and there are a number of same tree matches between panels. This procedure was based on exceptional visual agreement after seeking good agreements between individual series, typically using *t*-values over 12.0. Once that was done initial groupings were identified by seeking out groupings of highly matching series, where these were not same tree, those in the range *t*-values 8.0–12.0. These initial clusters were then used as the starting point to build up each chronology (a similar procedure was presented by Eckstein et al., 2009; Haneca and Daly 2014, 92). The series were averaged into a mean series and compared to the other dated tree-ring patterns. Series displaying a good agreement with the mean series, based on *t*-values over 5.0, were added to each chronology. Repeating this hierarchical procedure time and again, resulted in the final chronologies used here.

Through this procedure, 1281 of these series were ‘clustered’ into one of the three main Baltic groupings using a combination of *t*-values, a standard correlation statistic used for tree-ring data (Student 1908; Baillie and Pilcher 1973) and visual comparisons as described above. Each group was combined into final group chronologies. These comprise 552 Baltic 1 trees covering AD 1097–1636, 449 Baltic 2 trees covering AD 1142–1637, and 280 Baltic 3 trees covering AD 1228–1652. The remaining data comprises 82 that form a group known as Bowhill type in England and Vejdyb type in Denmark, which is close to Baltic 1 in origin,

which we will call here 2021BLT1B type, and 48 that form a rarer group also related to Baltic 1 that we have called 2021BLT1x. We will return to both these later.

Each of these three main groupings were combined first into a series of randomly selected sub-sequences, each of these of roughly similar replication. The intention was to produce a series of independent sub-series of broadly equal replication and the total numbers made aiming for series of c. 90 trees the nearest outcome. The sub-series for Baltic 1 thus comprised six sequences of 92 trees, Baltic 2 comprised five series of 89 or 90 trees, and Baltic 3 comprised three sub-series of 93 or 94 trees. Shortened group masters were produced by removing the parts of the final combined sequence comprising 1–3 trees only, these shortenings have the effect of taking more from the beginning than the end since each has a long ‘tail’ of inner tree-rings and a relatively blunt outer end. These shortened versions cover AD 1143–1626, AD 1186–1616, and AD 1292–1645 respectively. To separate these from the earlier datasets these are named as 2021BLT1, 2021BLT2 and 2021BLT3. The common interval for the final three series is AD 1292–1618. Note that only the three main series cover this common interval whilst the 14 sub-series of 2021BLT1, 2021BLT2 and 2021BLT3, and the less replicated 2021BLT1B and 2021BLT1x series do not cover all of this common period. For the rest of this discussion, we will consistently refer to the series type and their possible source areas as Baltic 1, Baltic 2 and Baltic 3, and these specific, new datasets as 2021BLT1, 2021BLT2 and 2021BLT3 etc.

The comparison of the sub-series provides some interesting detail. The three sub-series of 2021BLT3, for example, are remarkably uniform, average *t*-value = 26.6. The 2021BLT1 & 2021BLT2 subgroups exhibit

Fig. 6. The correlations (t -value) between the Hereford & Worcester composite sequence and a range of site chronologies (red) and regional chronologies (blue) decline with distance, generated using the statistical package ‘r’ (R Core Team 2021). (single column). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

less internal consistency, giving average t -values 2021BLT1 $t = 19.3$, 2021BLT2 $t = 16.7$, whilst still being remarkably uniform (in other words, the groups are each internally homogeneous). Sequence 2021BLT2 is slightly faster-grown at c. 1.44 mm/year averaged across its entire period, whilst 2021BLT1 and 2021BLT3 average c. 1.26 and 1.3 mm/year respectively. This in turn means that individual measurement series of ‘Baltic 2’ type would typically contain less rings than either of the others, when found in a similar width board. This is a pattern that has been observed in 16th century panels made from a combination of Baltic 1 and Baltic 2 sources. Each type has a handful of extremely strongly replicated signature years, two of 2021BLT3’s signature narrow years, AD 1403 and AD 1557, feature in 2021BLT1’s list of signature narrow years (see supplementary material). There are no coincident signature narrow or wide rings between 2021BLT2 and the other two groupings.

We can compare the three groups in several different ways. The shortened versions match as shown in Table 1. The matches between the subseries show that there is repeatable behaviour between the three groups (Table 2). (The larger replication in the main groups boosts the t -values).

Table 2 shows that each of the three main groups matches much more strongly internally, using these similarly weighted sequences, than they do to the other main groupings. It is also notable that the 2021BLT1 and 2021BLT3 sub-series appear to be slightly more similar to each other than either is to 2021BLT2 subseries. These three groups thus appear to represent regional groups of timber with the centres of each area far enough apart that there is minimal opportunity for intermediate types to appear between them. We could represent them as three areas

that do not overlap, and given the similar overall correlations, they appear to represent three areas set broadly as a triangle to each other, perhaps with Baltic 2 slightly further from the other two (Fig. 2).

4.1. Identifying the source of these groups

If we compare them to other regional datasets, in the form of a series of maps displaying the distribution of the t -values achieved, we can see their relative placement to these. Fig. 3 depicts the distribution for 2021BLT1, this map suggests that Baltic 1 correlates best with coastal Lithuania (the chronologies for Klaipeda mentioned above), and these correlations decrease with distance, both eastwards and westwards. Sequence 2021BLT2 (Fig. 4) correlates best with master chronologies for Southern Poland (Marek Krapiec pers comm), and then North Polish datasets (Ważny pers comm) (it cannot be ruled out that some timbers in the Gdansk chronologies might include what we would regard as Baltic 2 data). Sequence 2021BLT3 (Fig. 5) poorly matches these areas, instead it matches 2021BLT1 & 2021BLT2 strongly as we have seen (Table 1) and it then matches some Northern Polish chronologies rather weakly. However, it exhibits a very significant correlation with Vilnius local sequences. These observations mean that we can expand our assessment to incorporate a wider Baltic view (Fig. 2); On the basis of our new analysis, we would place Baltic 3 further away and east of the Polish, German and Scandinavian material. The Baltic 3 source is somewhere far enough from central Europe that it is dated by Baltic 1 and Baltic 2 types, rather than matching to central European datasets by itself.

For a long time, we have been waiting for known-origin oak data from the Baltic source area. The new data from Vilnius and Klaipeda can

Fig. 7. Map of the region south and east of the Baltic Sea, showing the major rivers and the places mentioned in this paper. The background map is from Natural Earth. Free vector and raster map data @ naturalearthdata.com. Natural Earth (public domain): <http://www.naturalearthdata.com>. The river data is from [Lehner and Grill \(2013\) \(www.hydrosheds.org\)](http://www.hydrosheds.org), accessed March 3, 2020). The map is generated using [QGIS.org, 2021](http://www.qgis.org). QGIS Geographic Information System. QGIS Association. <http://www.qgis.org> (two column).

Table 4

Correlation between the two outlying art-historical groups and a range of site and master chronologies.

	2021BLT1B	2021BLT1x
2021 Baltic 1 552 trees (Daly & Tyers this paper)	23.05	15.19
2021 Baltic 2 449 trees (Daly & Tyers this paper)	7.53	8.60
2021 Baltic 3 280 trees (Daly & Tyers this paper)	6.66	8.25
Klaipėda, Lithuania, oak (Vitas 2020)	16.80	6.97
Memel Klaipėda, Lithuania (Brazauskas 2006)	9.31	6.97
Vilnius Castle, Lithuania, oak, 20 timbers (Pukienė & Ožalas 2007)	8.94	4.38
St Jakobs Church, Riga, Latvia, 12 timbers (Daly & Zunde 2017 unpublished)	7.95	4.04
Gdansk, Poland (Ważny pers comm)	7.40	7.38
Cesis Castle, Latvia (Zunde pers comm)	6.86	5.72
Southwest Scania, Sweden (Lund University)	6.56	3.77
Jutland & Funen, Denmark (National Museum of Denmark)	5.58	3.30
Ystad area, Sweden (Lund University)	5.42	1.84
Lübeck, Germany (Hamburg Uni)	3.96	3.57

potentially guide us to the provenance of the art-historical material but this step requires us to make some assumptions about the *t*-value/distance relationship.

Table 3 shows the correlations between the Vilnius and Klaipėda chronologies. It seems clear that the two Klaipėda series have something in common, although we are uncertain whether one is a super-set of the other or whether the Klaipėda pair includes some components in

common and others not in common (Vitas 2020). Their replication levels are closer to them being ‘site’ chronologies rather than regional chronologies; note the relatively low correlations between the two locations. 2021BLT1 and 2021BLT3 strongly match to Klaipėda and Vilnius respectively (Figs. 3 and 5), and as the art chronologies are regional series, they match the other location strongly too. 2021BLT2 matches neither Klaipėda nor Vilnius especially strongly (Fig. 4).

Fig. 8. Map of the correlation between the Southern Baltic group ‘Baltic Bowhill/Vejdyb’ (2021BLT1B) and master and site chronologies for oak for Northern Europe. The correlation statistic used is Student’s *t*-test (Student 1908) where the tree-ring data is normalised according to Baillie and Pilcher (1973). The circle on the map is sized according to the *t*-value. The underlying tree-ring dataset is described in Daly (2007a) but recent additions to this dataset for Lithuania, Latvia and Russia are added. The background map is from Natural Earth. Free vector and raster map data @ [naturalearthdata.com](http://www.naturalearthdata.com). Natural Earth (public domain): <http://www.naturalearthdata.com>. The river data is from Lehner and Grill (2013) (www.hydrosheds.org, accessed March 3, 2020). The map is generated using QGIS.org, 2021. QGIS Geographic Information System. QGIS Association. <http://www.qgis.org> (two column).

5. A comparative dataset

Projects using tree-ring correlations to identify the likely provenance of timber typically use a spread of regional and local datasets to identify the likely origin of groups of timbers from a single item, such as a shipwreck, or from barrels, and other cargo items re-used in archaeological or other objects (e.g. Daly 2007a, 2007b; Daly et al., 2021b; Daly and Nymoen, 2008). Here however, we are attempting to provenance a group of three highly replicated datasets, that appear to derive from areas most of which have no regional chronology coverage, and from within which there are almost no local datasets of known origin, and there are no modern datasets long enough to provide our anchor points. For that reason, we need to be sure we understand the potential and limitations of using local datasets to circumscribe the point of origin of regional strength sequences, and also the likely correlations between regional datasets strung across the continent.

The *t*-value statistics, and other correlation measures, are not a straightforward proxy for distance, and they were never intended to be. Since strong well-replicated regional data match more strongly than local data, using them for provenance requires that we identify a typical set of parameters for inter-regional data distances in order to outline the relative placement of the Baltic chronologies, and we require regional to local data distances to see how the Baltic sequences should relate to the less replicated datasets from Vilnius, Klaipeda, Cesis & Riga, that are likely to be of reasonably local origin. To do this we compare a different regional sequence that is roughly the same replication, covers the same chronological period, and is from a geographically compact region. Herefordshire & Worcestershire are two small adjacent English counties;

they cover c 90 km × 50 km together. They are embedded within the very strong locally sourced framework of tree-ring data from England & Wales. They are surrounded by strong regional tree-ring sequences and they contain and are surrounded by many hundreds of separate site sequences of varying lengths and replication. Both counties contain many oak timber-framed buildings, usually made of long lived and slow growing oak timbers. Tree-ring data from this area matches strongly to local and regional datasets across England and Wales, and to regional data from Scotland, Ireland, the Netherlands, France and Germany.

A Hereford & Worcester composite sequence covering the same AD 1292–1618 period has a peak replication of c. 325 sequences, whilst our 2021BLT1, 2021BLT2 & 2021BLT3 series peak at c. 470, 400 and 260 trees respectively. We compare this with a set of c. 70 regional reference series, from across the British Isles, Ireland and continental Europe, up to 1500 km away, and separately against a series of c. 1000 local chronologies derived from buildings and archaeology (but deliberately excluding movable objects such as boats, barrels and panelling), these are up to 1000 kms away, so they are mostly but not exclusively from within the British Isles/Ireland (Fig. 6). Clearly there is a steady drop off by increasing distance for both types of comparison. Referring to the local series (in red) it can be seen that the strong matches from 2021BLT1 to Klaipeda ($t = 16.56$) and 2021BLT3 to Vilnius ($t = 13.39$) only occur in exceptional circumstances in our comparative data set, a few similar matches are seen between some data within c. 60 km, but only a handful of the comparison sites give higher correlations than 2021BLT1 gives with Klaipeda, whilst around a dozen nearby sites give higher correlations than those between 2021BLT3 and Vilnius, all are within 60 kms of the centre of the source area.

Fig. 9. The occurrence of oak panels from each art-historical group, through time: A: actual numbers, 1350–1640, B: percentages, 1450–1630, generated using the statistical package ‘r’ (R Core Team 2021). (single column). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

The regional comparison shows that longer distance matching can be expected than between the local series. The correlations observed between 2021BLT1, 2021BLT2 and 2021BLT3 (t-value range 10.7–12.1) appear to typically occur c. 250–350 km apart in the western European dataset.

The English comparative analysis, therefore, assuming that there are similar large-scale patterns of correlation in the eastern Baltic, suggests that Vilnius is likely to be within 60 km of the Baltic 3 source zone and Klaipeda is likely to be within 60 km of the Baltic 1 source zone. The low correlation between Vilnius and Klaipeda supports the assumption that both these datasets are from reasonably locally sourced and not long-distance traded timbers, note we cannot currently prove either is local, but hopefully this possibility will be eliminated as more local data sets are produced. Vilnius and Klaipeda are c. 285 km apart which also tallies with our tree-ring correlation-based estimate for the distance between 2021BLT1 & 2021BLT3. River trade is undoubtedly the vector for the movement of these boards, and one method of constraining their provenance is to place them onto the nearest major river system (Fig. 7). That approach points to the lower Nemunas region around Klaipeda for Baltic 1, and the Neris somewhere around Vilnius for Baltic 3. The Neris joins the Nemunas at Kaunas, then entering the Curonian lagoon, before exiting through Klaipeda into the Baltic.

The evidence from the correlations is that the Baltic 2 source region is somewhere further south (Fig. 4). In Poland the Vistula runs into Gdansk from south/south-eastwards. In the region around Warsaw there are 2 major tributaries; the Narew comes from eastwards, and the Bug from south-eastwards. Warsaw is c. 390 km from both Vilnius and Klaipeda, a distance again broadly compatible with the correlations of 2021BLT2 to both 2021BLT1 and 2021BLT3. Perhaps therefore we can place Baltic 2 in the region around the confluence of these three river systems (the Vistula and its two main tributaries). The previously noted lower inter-correlations within the 2021BLT2 group might suggest that this source area is larger than the source areas for 2021BLT1 & 2021BLT3.

These widely spread distributions may perhaps be due to limited opportunities for exploitable access routes into the oak woods along these rivers. This might explain the apparent lack of intermediate source zones. Botanical distribution maps show that oaks are widely distributed in this region (e.g. de Rigo et al., 2016). However, such maps cannot show the fine detail of these distributions, at large scale they are often based on records within 10 km or 50 km mapping squares. Fieldwork along the upper part of the Dvina/Daugava River indicates that oaks are only present in the floodplain there at a handful of locations (Bulat Khasanov pers comm; Khasanov et al., 2021). That river system flows

into Riga and may be the source of a different group of later oak imports. It would be interesting to know if there are, or were once, disjunct distributions of high canopy oak woodland along the Vistula, Neris and Nemunas rivers, since these could perhaps independently point towards the likeliest source zones. The group of similar long lived and straight grained oak trees surviving in the Białowieża Forest on the Polish/-Belarusian border may perhaps owe their survival to the absence of large rivers in their region.

6. Two further separate baltic sources?

As mentioned above, apart from the three main groups, two smaller but distinct groups were identified. Bowhill type was originally identified in the UK from a group of ceiling boards in Exeter from a house of that name (Groves 2002), and almost immediately matched a set of panelling in Winchester (Lewis 1995; Miles and Haddon-Reece 1996). These were so similar that there were even some initial suggestions that they were derived from a single shipment of timber, however subsequent experiences would suggest instead that they were from a common source. Pascale Fraiture subsequently used strong Bowhill matching as a grouping for some Flemish panels (Fraiture 2007, 130), and it was then found that one of us had independently identified amongst her material a grouping clustered around the Vejdyb boat sequences (Daly 1997). In tree-ring terms these are part of the same group (Bowhill correlates with Vejdyb giving a *t*-value of 11.68). This type has therefore been independently identified within several different groups of Baltic data by independent workers. It is found in both English and Flemish panels, as well as in panelling and archaeological material within a relatively narrow time frame, the decades either side of 1500. This material is slower-grown than 2021BLT1, c. 1.13 mm/year on average, and these 82 examples have on average over 213 rings in each sample. In fact, this material appears to be longer-lived than any other Baltic group. Our 2021BLT1B sequence matches 2021BLT1 very strongly (see Tables 2 and 4 *t*-value 23.05), it has a slightly higher match to Klaipeda than the stronger 2021BLT1 sequence and its lower matching to 2021BLT2 & 2021BLT3 suggests it was perhaps closer to Klaipeda than 2021BLT1 (Fig. 8). The South Sweden, Poland and Vilnius matchings support a near-Baltic 1 source zone for this type. The limited period during which this type occurs, and its distinctive slow growth character, perhaps indicates that it was a particular forest area within or on the edge of the Baltic 1 region that was exported for a limited period.

A similarly distinctive later group, 2021BLT1x (*n* = 48), occurring in the decades either side of 1600, is also present. Like 2021BLT1B, it also matches 2021BLT1 very strongly, but its shorter overlap (although that overlap is 168 years long) with 2021BLT1B is perhaps the reason for the lower match to that group (Table 2). 2021BLT1x matches to 2021BLT2 and 2021BLT3, Klaipeda and Northern Poland (Table 4), but it does not significantly match South Swedish, Danish or German data (although it is relatively poorly replicated for such long-distance matching). Very few of the 2021BLT1x individual series match 2021BLT3 so although locating this source is more difficult than the others, we might suggest that it lies outside our triangle, to the north of 2021BLT1, perhaps somewhere along the coast of Latvia.

The source of the Baltic oak, as indicated by the dendrochronological groupings, has a tendency to change over time. In Fig. 9A the material included in the three groups and the two smaller sub-groups is illustrated through time. This is all the data, sorted on its last heartwood ring, which is used as a proxy for the heartwood/sapwood boundary. The actual numbers are illustrated in Fig. 9A and then as a percentage for just the better replicated section in Fig. 9B.

The 2021BLT1 (blue) and the slightly different 2021BLT1B (orange) types dominate the beginnings of the trade in this product, from around 1450 to a peak around 1520s–30s. Then the 2021BLT2 (yellow) group increases. The 2021BLT1 source does not disappear however, so we are not seeing a depletion of the oaks from this source, and this group increases in frequency again towards the end of the 16th century. The

dominance of 2021BLT3 (green) after c 1600 is very clear.

The gradual change over two centuries of oak timber trade from the Baltic region to western Europe, that the study of painted panels here demonstrates, can be juxtaposed with written records that show this trade. Gdansk had its trading heyday 2nd half of the 15th and to 1st half 16th century according to Ważny and Eckstein (1987). They mention the Vistula as the main source of the timber shipped from Gdansk. This is thus represented by the Baltic 2 group. If our thesis that the Baltic 1 group is from trees harvested around coastal Lithuania, these might represent the oak shipped from Königsberg and Courland that we also see in written records. Bonde et al. (1995) present the port origin of wainscots shipped through the Danish Sound (Bonde et al. 1995, 203). These records start in 1562 and show that Gdansk still dominates over Königsberg and Courland in the mid-16th century but gradually declines such that by 1605 the three ports share equally a third of shipments. The decline of Gdansk as a timber-exporting port is clear in the data presented here in Fig. 9. Both the Baltic 1 groups and Baltic 2 decline from the end of the 16th century. The Baltic 3 source, from further inland in present day Lithuania, could supply the oak needs by around 1600, and this could be what can be seen in the Danish Sound Toll Registers. Of course, here should be mentioned the introduction of timber exported from wholly other regions, Norway, Sweden and indeed the new worlds, from the mid-17th century. Certainly, the dendrochronological evidence summarised in Fig. 9 builds on gaps in the written record, and invites a new interrogation of the historical information.

7. Discussion

Thirty-five years ago, tree-ring data identified that the art-historical datasets were derived from an extensive continuous trade of oak planks, boards etc from the territories on the east and south Baltic coasts (Ballie et al. 1985). This paper utilises a robust art-historical dataset that clarifies the division into three main Baltic groups, including for the first time a useful dataset to represent Baltic 3. This attempt to identify where these groups come from was partly driven by the sapwood data of Sohar et al. (2012) and our concerns to apply regionally appropriate sapwood estimates to the Baltic datasets. From the evidence presented here, we now think that we can continue applying the Northern Polish sapwood estimate (Ważny 1990) for objects belonging to the Baltic 2 group, but it may be suggested that smaller sapwood estimates are appropriate for objects that are identified as Baltic 1 and Baltic 3 types and the other groups. However, none should be as narrow as the Sohar et al. numbers, which are from further north than any of the source zones proposed here. We are making the datasets that we describe in this paper available for researchers (see supplementary material), so that new analyses can identify to which group an oak belongs, by comparing it to all groups, and of course to other oak datasets for the region, and identifying the highest correlations. Researchers will in future be able to compare new and legacy tree-ring datasets (e.g. those housed in the repository for dendrochronological data from artworks (<https://dendro4art.org>)) with the robust Baltic chronologies now made available in this analysis.

This analysis has strongly indicated that the geographical origin of the Baltic 1, Baltic 2 and Baltic 3 art-historical groups should be seen as a widely spaced triangular area, rather than for example a linear one representing exploitation further and further up a single river system. Each zone seems to be surprisingly discrete, and potentially quite compact. There is little evidence for intermediate sources of any significance. Additionally, it is clear that the key to any discussion of their source must be the river systems in the area. These rivers principally flow westwards and northwards where they connect to the east and south Baltic trading towns at the mouths of these rivers. These Hanseatic towns frequently get referred to in customs documents of the period (see e.g. Salzman 1952; Childs 1986, 2010; Bonde et al., 1997).

It is clear, through the tree-ring dataset that we describe here, that there are still gaps in our knowledge, regarding dendrochronological research into the historic trade of oak from the south and east Baltic

regions. What we present here is a proposal based on the current data network available across the likely source area. We have combined these with hypothetical reconstructions, based on potential distances between these sources and their proximity to the steadily developing local data network, and placing our trade firmly onto the regional river systems. The validity of these theories will have to await further confirmation as and when additional localised datasets are analysed.

The continuing puzzle surrounds Riga. Our evidence indicates groups 2021BLT1, 2021BLT1B and 2021BLT1x each came from around Klaipeda or perhaps between Gdansk, Klaipeda and Riga, the likeliest Riga component that we suggest, group 2021BLT1x, is very small. There is a possibility that the Klaipeda and Riga export trade came from a single overlapping geographical area, covered by the 2021BLT1, 1a and 1x types but that we cannot see a division in this data due to geographical overlap.

The insights gained from the analysis of the 1450–1655 Baltic material may help us subsequently approach the earlier Baltic material that is seen in the west from c. 1300, and equally we can use similar techniques into the post-1655 era where there is both a dramatic fall off in the Baltic 1, 2 & 3 sources and an expansion of alternative sources, including some currently thought to originate further to the east and north of these groupings. The earlier Baltic group comprises datasets found in archaeological material, primarily from boats (including a handful of finds of ships/boats with cargo), numerous barrels, coffins and early decorative pieces such as altarpieces and ecclesiastical sculpture and furniture, the latter grouping is primarily seen in furniture, and may be synonymous with the ‘northern wainscot’ documented in furniture records (Bowett 2012).

8. Conclusions

Through the analysis of artworks from the 14th to 17th centuries, we see that a large proportion of their boards come from the region to south and east of the Baltic Sea. Two groups that were identified dendrochronologically in the 1980s (Baltic 1 and Baltic 2) and a third group (Baltic 3) more tentatively identified (Hillam and Tyers 1995) are here, three decades later, confirmed and strengthened. Two sub-groups related to the Baltic 1 group are also identified. We also demonstrate that the three groups reflect a chronological progression, as the exploitation of oaks from these regions spread and diversified, as the lucrative and extensive trade westwards continued. We suggest in this paper that these three groups represent the exploitation of oak trees in three distinct and separate regions, and these reflect sources associated with the major rivers draining into the south and east Baltic Sea coasts. The earliest Baltic 1 group represents trees from the lower Nemunas river region around Klaipeda. For the Baltic 2 group we believe that the source was further south around the confluence of the Vistula and its two main tributaries: the Narew and the Bug. We place the later Baltic 3 group source on the Neris River somewhere around Vilnius.

We present these three groups in the form of master chronologies for each group, 2021BLT1 (and related sub-groups 2021BLT1B and 2021BLT1x), 2021BLT2 and 2021BLT3, in the supplementary material. As these contain some of the same tree-ring series as the older BALTIC1 and BALTIC2 chronologies, these new masters replace the old. These can now be adopted by dendrochronologists as the basis for identifying the Baltic provenance of many cultural heritage objects. By making these datasets fully available, we ensure that all researchers are referring to the same dataset.

9. Supplementary material

The master chronologies for the new 2021BLT-groups described in this article are made available in the supplementary material. Additionally, a summary of the signature years in the BLT groups is presented (80% signatures where 10 or more trees are represented). Finally, there is a matrix of internal correlation (*t*-value (TBP)) of a random selection

of the series from each of the groups identified, to illustrate the clustering of the dataset. The supplementary material is found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4590258>.

Author contributions

Aoife Daly: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Funding acquisition. Ian Tyers: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Data curation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

None.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2022.105550>.

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